

THE EFFECT OF PRESSURE AND TEMPERATURE ON THE ADSORPTION METHOD FOR EXTRACTING N-PARAFFINS FROM GASOLINE FRACTIONS

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Abstract

Gasoline fractions from most crude oils contain a significant amount of n-paraffin hydrocarbons. Primary processing of these oils yields gasolines containing 30-40% n-alkanes, which significantly lowers the octane number of the gasoline. N-paraffins present in gasoline fractions are valuable raw materials for various chemical productions. For instance, n-paraffins extracted from gasoline fractions can serve as solvents in the production of polyethylene, polypropylene, plastics, synthetic rubbers, pharmaceuticals, in the food industry for extracting edible fats, in wool production and processing, and as components in adhesives, varnishes, paints, and quick-drying rubber cements [1].

The extraction of normal paraffins from gasoline fractions can be achieved through various methods in modern petrochemical industries. Rectification-based separation of n-paraffins allows obtaining concentrates with up to 80% purity. However, deeper rectification leads to significant economic costs. Adsorption-based separation of n-paraffins offers a more economical process, enabling the production of n-paraffin concentrates with up to 99% purity [2,3].

Keyword: N-alkanes, Adsorption, Pressure, Output derivatives, Zeolite.

Introduction

Adsorptive separation of n-paraffins from petroleum products can also be highly beneficial for producing components for high-octane gasoline. A significant portion of high-octane gasoline currently produced in the petroleum industry is obtained using ethyl fluid, leading to atmospheric pollution. One way to obtain high-octane gasoline without adding ethyl fluid is the widespread development of processes for isomerizing C5-C8 n-paraffins.

However, in isomerization processes, based on equilibrium conditions, complete conversion of n-paraffins cannot be achieved, significantly affecting the octane number. Removing n-paraffins from reaction products can increase the octane number by 7-9 points. N-paraffins can be separated as a commercial product or returned to the process. Recycling n-paraffins and fully processing them create the opportunity for the efficient use of the medium-temperature isomerization process on a zeolite catalyst.

Separating normal paraffins from the feedstock and directing them into the isomerization reactor can significantly increase the productivity of the isomerization unit. This raises the challenge of developing a combined isomerization and adsorption process within a single technology framework.

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The content of normal paraffin hydrocarbons in straight-run gasolines amounts to up to 40%. In secondary gasolines, this content is up to 15% n-paraffin hydrocarbons. N-pentane and hexane, which are valuable raw materials for the petrochemical industry, have a negative impact on gasoline quality. N-paraffin hydrocarbons can be used in the production of aldehydes, alcohols, and acids [4].

High-purity n-hexane can be used as a solvent in the production of plastics and synthetic rubbers, pharmaceuticals, and in the food industry for extracting edible fats from various plant seeds. Thanks to its high volatility, pure n-hexane can also be used as a component in adhesives, varnishes, printing inks, and quick-drying rubber cements.

Purpose of the research

The aim of this study was to investigate the influence of pressure on the process of adsorptive extraction of paraffins from gasoline fractions.

Experimental part

To conduct research on the fundamental principles of the separation process of light gasoline fractions, synthetic zeolite CaA was employed. The experience gained from studying a series of regularities in the adsorption of n-paraffins was instrumental. When investigating the regularities of the process of adsorptive separation of n-heptane and n-octane in a stationary layer of zeolite, various model mixtures were utilized.

In this regard, the adsorption equilibrium and kinetics of n-pentane and n-hexane were examined on a micro-laboratory flow weighing setup [14], whose operation principle is based on assessing the change in mass of zeolite during the adsorption or desorption of the substance under study, introduced through the zeolite in a hydrogen stream or during its adsorption. The micro-laboratory setup (Figure 2.1) comprises the following components: a heating and raw material vaporization unit, an adsorption unit with a mass measuring

device, a differential transformer system of mass registration sensors. The setup is equipped with automatic temperature control and recording. For hydrogen purification from oxygen and moisture, a gas preparation unit is included. 2-3 grams of zeolite, weighed on analytical scales, were loaded into the adsorber and activated. For this purpose, hydrogen was introduced into the adsorption unit, and the temperature was gradually raised to 500°C. The zeolite was held at this temperature until a constant weight was achieved.

Adsorption of n-alkanes was conducted at temperatures of 275°C and 335°C and pressures of approximately 28 atm. The adsorber was loaded with 75 grams of zeolite, and the adsorption volume was 110 cm³.

The fundamental regularities of the adsorption process were studied on a continuously operated setup with a zeolite bed 1.1 meters in length. The setup reproduced technological parameters such as temperature, pressure, zeolite load, hydrogen-feed ratio, hydrogen feed exchange rate, and duration of individual stages of the cycle.

Experiments on the setup were conducted as follows: 1000 grams of weighed zeolite were loaded into the adsorber. A layer of ceramic packing 0.4 meters high was placed on the zeolite. After sealing the system, hydrogen was introduced into the adsorbers at a rate of 100-200 nl/h, and the temperature of the zeolite bed was gradually increased using four electric heaters applied to the outer wall of the adsorber. The temperature was raised to 400-450°C. After drying the zeolite, the temperature in the adsorber was reduced to the required level, and the feed (during adsorption) and hydrogen (during desorption) were alternately introduced into it. The feed and hydrogen were fed into the built-in feeder at the top of the adsorber and into the layer of ceramic

packing, which also served to distribute the flow evenly across the adsorber's cross-section.

To maintain stable pressure in the adsorber and separators during the adsorption stage, a small amount of hydrogen was introduced into the adsorber.

One of the significant factors influencing the process of adsorptive extraction of n-paraffins from gasoline fractions is the process pressure.

We obtained adsorption isotherms of n-heptane and n-octane by zeolite CaA at various temperatures in the range of partial pressures from 7 to 70 kPa. The amount of hydrocarbon adsorbed by the zeolite increases with increasing partial pressure at a given temperature. For instance, the maximum adsorption of n-heptane at 345°C increases from 3% to 6% by mass with increasing pressure from 95 to 680 kPa. The adsorption of n-heptane at these temperatures and pressure ranges is respectively 5 and 7% by mass.

From the adsorption isotherms of n-heptane and n-octane by zeolite CaA, it can be observed that to achieve the same maximum adsorption of these hydrocarbons, n-heptane must have higher partial pressures than n-octane or lower adsorption temperatures. Thus, the data above indicate a greater dependence of the adsorption of lower molecular weight n-paraffins on temperature and partial pressure.

Since the saturation of each granule of zeolite CaA with n-paraffins depends on the diffusion rate of adsorbed molecules within the granule, kinetic curves of adsorption were determined on a micro-laboratory setup. Figure 1 shows the kinetic curves of n-octane adsorption by zeolite CaA from its mixture with hydrogen at partial pressures in the range of 6-60 kPa. As can be seen, an increase in the partial pressure of n-octane not only increases the equilibrium adsorption but also the rate of hydrocarbon absorption by the zeolite.

Figure 1: Kinetic adsorption curves of n-C6H14 on zeolite CaA at partial pressures of n-alkane: 1-6; 2-14; 3-25; 4-50; 5-60 kPa

If it takes 20 minutes to reach equilibrium at a partial pressure of n-octane of 6.0 kPa at 275°C, then at a partial pressure of 60 kPa, it is achieved in 8 minutes. The process speed significantly increases with temperature rise. At 335°C, the time to reach equilibrium for n-octane decreases to 15 minutes in the first case and 3.0 minutes in the second case. Thus, the efficiency of n-paraffin adsorption from the gas stream with increased partial pressure increases with the temperature rise of the process, and the process temperature should be preferably not below 335°C.

The implementation of the process under dynamic conditions to obtain deeply dearomatized gasoline cannot be characterized solely by adsorption isotherms and

kinetic curves. More significant data are obtained on adsorption setups under dynamic conditions, which allows evaluating not only the zeolite capacity for n-paraffins until saturation and the rate of their absorption but also the capacity before n-paraffins breakthrough into the outgoing product from the adsorber and the mass exchange zone formed in the process.

Table 1 presents data on the influence of the partial pressure of n-paraffins on the adsorption properties of zeolite under conditions of the same total process pressure (1.4 MPa) and temperature (345°C).

Table 1.

The influence of the partial pressure of n-paraffins on the adsorption properties of zeolite CaA.

Temperature, °C	Pressure, MPa	Hydrogen Desorption Rate		Feedstock n-Paraffin Content, %	Cyclic Load of n-Paraffins, %	Linear Feed Rate of Feedstock, cm/s	Partial pressure of n-paraffins, mmHg	Zeolite capacity, %	
		raw vol.	Working vol.					Before breakthrough	Until saturation
345	14/1,4	240	32,6	23,5	1,6	2,5	2060	2,19	3,01
345	14/1,4	215	32,6	38,0	3,0	2,5	3400	3,40	4,11
345	14/1,4	215	32,6	53,0	4,0	2,5	4600	4,80	5,81

The results were obtained on a pilot plant with a zeolite operating time of about 1,500 hours. The linear feed rate for adsorption (2.5 cm/sec), desorption conditions (hydrogen treatment frequency, desorption time, etc.) in the experiments were consistent. The investigated range of fluctuation in the partial pressure of n-paraffins in the adsorption stage was determined by the varying content of n-paraffins in the feedstock, obtained by diluting the original feedstock with denormalized material. From the presented data, it can be inferred that increasing the partial pressure of n-paraffins in the feedstock from 2060 mm Hg to 4600 mm Hg

(i.e., the cyclic load of n-paraffins on the zeolite from 1.6 to 4.0% by weight) leads to a reduction in the mass transfer zone from 84.5 to 66 cm and, as a result, an increase in the zeolite capacities to breakthrough and saturation by 2.1 and 2 times, respectively.

Figure 2 shows the output adsorption curves of n-paraffins by zeolite CaA obtained in these experiments. As seen, their shapes differ, with the curve being most sharply defined under conditions of maximum partial pressure of n-alkanes; the other curves have a dispersed shape.

Figure 2. Output curves of adsorption of normal alkanes from feedstock with normal alkane content: 1-53.1; 2-39.2; 3-22.3 %

It was found that when studying the kinetics of adsorption of normal alkanes by zeolite, with an increase in the partial pressure of vapors and normal alkanes, the saturation time of zeolite granules is reduced by approximately 20%. The study of adsorption of normal alkanes using zeolite CaA and a adsorption stage duration of 2.5 minutes showed that the absorption of normal alkanes should be conducted at a temperature of 330°C and at a partial pressure of normal alkanes ranging from 25 to 50 kPa, especially when processing feedstock with a content of 25-35% mass alkanes. Kinetic curves of adsorption of octane by zeolite CaA from its mixture with hydrogen at partial pressures of normal alkanes in the range of (6-60 kPa) are shown. As seen, the increase in the partial pressure of the normal alkane not only increases the equilibrium adsorption capacity but also the rate of hydrocarbon absorption by zeolite.

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